

Synthesis and antifungal potential of 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives

Nisheeth Rastogi^{a*}, Padam Kant^b, Rakesh Sethi^b, Darwin Anil Harrison^a and Sarveshwar Shukla^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Lucknow Christian Post-Graduate College, Lucknow-226 018, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : nisheethrastogi2003@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007, Uttar Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Jai Narain Post-Graduate College, Lucknow-226 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : 3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (1a-d) were prepared by treating 4-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazines successively with alcoholic potassium hydroxide-carbon disulphide and hydrazine hydrate, which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate, carbon disulphide, benzoic acid, benzoin, phenacyl bromide, phenyl isothiocyanate, formic acid, chloroacetyl chloride, benzaldehyde and isatin gave condensed bridgehead heterocycles (triazolo-thiadiazoles and triazolo-thiadiazines). The structures of the compounds were established with the help of elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, PMR and Mass). Compounds were screened for their antimycotic potential against human pathogenic fungi.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazole, condensed bridgehead heterocycle, triazolo-thiadiazole, triazolo-thiadiazine, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Various 1,2,4-triazole derivatives have been reported to possess diverse types of biological activities such as analgesic, antiinflammatory¹, antitumor², antimycobacterial³, anticancer⁴, anticonvulsant⁵, diuretic⁶, antimicrobial⁷ and antidiabetic⁸. 1,3,4-Thiadiazoles have also been found to show antibacterial⁹, antimicrobial¹⁰, antiinflammatory¹¹ and anticonvulsant¹² activities. Derivatives of 1,2,4-triazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole condensed system have been found to possess varying pharmacological activities such as antitumor¹³, antiinflammatory¹⁴, CNS stimulant¹⁵, anticancer¹⁶ and antimicrobial¹⁷. Triazoles fused with six membered heterocyclic rings have also been found to possess diverse applications in medicinal field¹⁸. In the light of biological activity profile of triazoles, thiadiazoles, triazolo-thiadiazole and triazolo-thiadiazine systems, in the present communication condensed bridgehead heterocycles have been synthesized.

The required 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (1a-d), which show thione-thiol

type of tautomerism were prepared by treating 4-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazines¹⁹ successively with alcoholic potassium hydroxide-carbon disulphide and hydrazine hydrate. Benzoylhydrazines were obtained by the hydrazinolysis of methyl 4-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoates which in turn were obtained by the reaction of methyl paraben with chlorobenzyl chlorides. The reaction of 1a-d with hydrazine hydrate, carbon disulphide, benzoic acid, benzoin, phenacyl bromide, phenyl isothiocyanate, formic acid, chloroacetyl chloride, benzaldehyde and isatin gave 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles (2a-d), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole-6(5H)-thiones (3a-d), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-6-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (4a-d), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-6,7-diphenyl-5H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (5a-d), 6-phenyl-3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-7H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-[1,3,4]thiadiazines (6a-d), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-6-aminophenyl-5H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (7a-d), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-

*Address for correspondence : 231/103 Ka, Bagh Macca, Khinni Tare, Raja Bazar, Lucknow-226 003, Uttar Pradesh, India.

1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**8a-d**), 3-{4'-(chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-7*H*-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazine-6(5*H*)-ones (**9a-d**), 6-phenyl-5,6-dihydro-3-{4'-(chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**10a-d**) and 3-[[4'-(chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl]-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]-iminoisatins (**11a-d**) respectively.

Antifungal activity :

Compounds **1-11** were screened for their *in vitro* antifungal potential against human pathogenic yeasts viz. *Candida albicans* (CA), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (CN), *Sporothrix schenckii* (SS) and mycelial dermatophytic fungi viz. *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF). The compounds were tested at 100 µg/mL concentration in DMSO by Tube Dilution Technique²⁰. The spore suspension of 10⁵ spores/mL was used for this purpose. The drug dilutions were made serially. The test was performed at 29 °C and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) in µg/mL was recorded by visual observation after 24–72 h incubation. Suitable controls : broth control (without infection), growth control (with infection), solvent DMSO, drug controls (all test compounds) and fluconazole (as standard drug) were set under identical conditions. The last tube with no apparent growth of organism represented the MIC of compounds. Among the compounds **1a-d**, **1a-c** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against TM and AF while **1d** showed MIC 3.12 and 6.25 µg/mL against TM and AF respectively. Compound **2a** showed MIC 3.12 µg/mL against both TM and AF whereas **2c** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against both TM and AF. Compound **2b** showed MIC 3.12 and 6.25 µg/mL against TM and AF respectively. **2d** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against AF only. Among **3a-d**, only **3a** and **3b** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against AF and 12.5 µg/mL against TM. **4a** and **4b** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against both the fungi TM and AF. **5a** and **5b** were found to show MIC 6.25 µg/mL against both the fungi TM and AF. Out of **6a-d**, only **6b** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against TM. **7a** showed MIC 3.12 µg/mL against both TM and AF while **7b** showed MIC 3.12 and 12.5 µg/ml against TM and AF respectively. **7a** and **7b** also showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against CA and SS. Compounds **8a** and **8b** both showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against CN and 3.12 µg/mL against TM and AF. **8c** showed MIC 6.25 and 3.12 µg/mL against TM and AF respectively whereas **8d** showed

MIC 6.25 µg/mL against CN and 3.12 µg/mL against TM and AF. **9a** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against CA and CN and 3.12 µg/mL against TM and AF while **9b** showed MIC 6.25 against CA, CN, TM and AF. **9c** and **9d** both showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against CN, 12.5 µg/mL against TM and 3.12 µg/mL against AF. Compounds **10b** and **10d** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against TM and AF. **11a** and **11b** both showed MIC 3.12 µg/mL against TM and 12.5 µg/mL against AF. Compound **11d** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against both TM and AF respectively. In the last, synthesized compounds have shown varying degree of antifungal activity against human pathogenic fungi although they have shown their major potential against dermatophytes like *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF). However, none of the compounds was found to show antifungal activity comparable to that of standard drug, fluconazole.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes in sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer. PMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent. TMS was taken as internal reference. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol-JMS-300 spectrometer at 70 eV. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) data were obtained on Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by TLC silica gel G plates and spots were located by iodine vapors.

3-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (**1a**); 3-{4'-(3''-Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (**1b**); 3-{4'-(4''-Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (**1c**) and 3-{4'-(2'',4''-Dichlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (**1d**) were synthesized by the literature method²¹.

1a : Yield 70%, m.p. 179–181 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3400, 3124 (NH and NH₂), 1247 (-CH₂O-), 1092 (C=S), 748 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 367 (M⁺), 369 (M+2) (Found : C, 54.04; H, 3.88; N, 16.77. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₃ClN₄OS : C, 54.13; H, 3.90; N, 16.84%); **1b** : Yield 78%, m.p. 180–182 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3408, 3134 (NH and NH₂), 1251 (-CH₂O-), 1100 (C=S), 749 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 367 (M⁺), 369 (M+2) (Found : C, 54.07; H, 3.85; N,

16.78. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{13}ClN_4OS$: C, 54.13; H, 3.90; N, 16.84%.

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles (**2a-d**) :

Triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.01 mol) in DMF (25 mL) were refluxed for 8–10 h or until the evolution of hydrogen sulphide ceased. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from aqueous DMF. **2a** : Yield 67%, m.p. 177–178 °C; PMR : 3.32 (1H, s, NH), 5.24 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 5.55 (4H, s, NH₂), 7.09–8.18 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 330 (M⁺), 332 (M+2) (Found : C, 54.41; H, 4.45; N, 25.34. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{15}ClN_6O$: C, 54.46; H, 4.53; N, 25.41%); **2b** : Yield 70%, m.p. 177–178 °C (Found : C, 54.41; H, 4.50; N, 25.45. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{15}ClN_6O$: C, 54.46; H, 4.53; N, 25.41%); **2c** : Yield 78%, m.p. 165–166 °C (Found : C, 54.39; H, 4.48; N, 25.37. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{15}ClN_6O$: C, 54.46; H, 4.53; N, 25.41%); **2d** : Yield 66%, m.p. 167–168 °C (Found : C, 45.30; H, 3.46; N, 21.09. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{14}Cl_2N_6O$: C, 45.34; H, 3.52; N, 21.15%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole-6(5H)-thiones (**3a-d**) :

A mixture of triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol), carbon disulphide (0.015 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.015 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 mL) were refluxed for 9–12 h or until the evolution of hydrogen sulphide ceased. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured on crushed ice and acidified with acetic acid. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from aqueous DMF. **3a** : Yield 70%, m.p. 166–167 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3220 (NH), 1623 (C=N), 1245 (-CH₂O-), 1130 (C=S), 758 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 374 (M⁺), 376 (M+2) (Found : C, 51.23; H, 2.86; N, 14.90. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}ClN_4OS_2$: C, 51.26; H, 2.93; N, 14.95%); **3b** : Yield 70%, m.p. 144–146 °C (Found : C, 51.23; H, 2.97; N, 14.90. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}ClN_4OS_2$: C, 51.26; H, 2.93; N, 14.95%); **3c** : Yield 67%, m.p. 178–180 °C (Found : C, 51.21; H, 2.88; N, 14.90. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}ClN_4OS_2$: C, 51.26; H, 2.93; N, 14.95%); **3d** : Yield 67%, m.p. 180–182 °C (Found : C, 45.90; H, 2.20; N, 13.60. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}Cl_2N_4OS_2$: C, 46.04; H, 2.24; N, 13.69%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-6-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**4a-d**) :

A mixture of triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and benzoic

acid (0.01 mol) in phosphorus oxychloride (15 mL) were heated in an oil bath at 120 °C for 2–5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice cold water and neutralized with aqueous potassium carbonate solution. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH (5 : 1). **4a** : Yield 56%, m.p. 192–194 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3045 (C-H aromatic stretching), 1624 (C=N), 1611 (C=C), 1242 (-CH₂O-), 750 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 418 (M⁺), 420 (M+2) (Found : C, 62.95; H, 3.48; N, 13.35. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{15}ClN_4OS$: C, 63.08; H, 3.58; N, 13.38%); **4b** : Yield 66%, m.p. 211–212 °C (Found : C, 62.98; H, 3.45; N, 13.30. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{15}ClN_4OS$: C, 63.08; H, 3.58; N, 13.38%); **4c** : Yield 66%, m.p. 230–232 °C (Found : C, 62.98; H, 3.52; N, 13.31. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{15}ClN_4OS$: C, 63.08; H, 3.58; N, 13.38%); **4d** : Yield 65%, m.p. 196–197 °C (Found : C, 58.20; H, 2.89; N, 12.27. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{14}Cl_2N_4OS$: C, 58.27; H, 3.09; N, 12.36%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-6,7-diphenyl-5H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (**5a-d**) :

A mixture of triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and benzoin (0.01 mol) in isopropyl alcohol (20 mL) were heated to get a clear solution. To this, hot solution of potassium hydroxide (2 N, 10 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 30 min. On cooling solid separated out, which was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH (5 : 1). **5a** : Yield 56%, m.p. 140–142 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3228 (NH), 3039 (C-H aromatic stretching), 1620 (C=N), 1610 (C=C), 1245 (-CH₂O-), 750 (C-Cl), MS (*m/z*) : 508 (M⁺), 510 (M+2) (Found : C, 68.30; H, 4.08; N, 10.96. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{21}ClN_4OS$: C, 68.43; H, 4.12; N, 11.01%); **5b** : Yield 50%, m.p. 134–136 °C (Found : C, 68.30; H, 4.04; N, 10.94. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{21}ClN_4OS$: C, 68.43; H, 4.12; N, 11.01%); **5c** : Yield 45%, m.p. 120–122 °C (Found : C, 68.39; H, 4.08; N, 10.97. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{21}ClN_4OS$: C, 68.43; H, 4.12; N, 11.01%); **5d** : Yield 50%, m.p. 115–117 °C (Found : C, 67.97; H, 3.56; N, 10.16. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{20}Cl_2N_4OS$: C, 68.08; H, 3.68; N, 10.31%).

6-Phenyl-3-{4'-(chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-7H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (**6a-d**) :

A mixture of triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol), phenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (2.5 g) in DMF

(25 mL) were heated under reflux for 12–15 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water and recrystallised from aqueous DMF. **6a** : Yield 50%, m.p. 167–168 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3041 (C–H aromatic stretching), 1625 (C=N), 1521 (C–N), 1255 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 761 (C–Cl); PMR : 5.21 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 4.10 (2H, s, $-\text{SCH}_2-$), 7.10–7.98 (13H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : 432 (M^+), 434 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 63.70; H, 3.90; N, 11.83. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 63.81; H, 3.93; N, 12.94%); **6b** : Yield 50%, m.p. 167–168 °C (Found : C, 63.70; H, 3.90; N, 11.83. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 63.81; H, 3.93; N, 12.94%); **6c** : Yield 56%, m.p. 170–172 °C (Found : C, 63.61; H, 3.90; N, 11.86. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 63.81; H, 3.93; N, 12.94%); **6d** : Yield 56%, m.p. 178–179 °C (Found : C, 59.02; H, 3.47; N, 11.88. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{OS}$: C, 59.10; H, 3.42; N, 11.99%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-6-aminophenyl-5H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (7a-d) :

To a solution of triazoles **1a-d** (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 mL), phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added and heated under reflux for 15–20 h and poured into ice cold water. The solid so obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from CHCl_3 : MeOH (5 : 1). **7a** : Yield 66%, m.p. 170–172 °C; PMR : 5.24 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 7.15–7.92 (13H, m, Ar-H), 9.77 (1H, s, NH); MS (m/z) : 433 (M^+), 435 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 62.86; H, 3.76; N, 13.37. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 62.93; H, 3.81; N, 13.34%); **7b** : Yield 68%, m.p. 156–157 °C (Found : C, 62.86; H, 3.84; N, 13.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 62.93; H, 3.81; N, 13.34%); **7c** : Yield 66%, m.p. 135–137 °C (Found : C, 62.89; H, 3.78; N, 13.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 62.93; H, 3.81; N, 13.34%); **7d** : Yield 70%, m.p. 156–157 °C (Found : C, 56.33; H, 3.16; N, 14.90. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{OS}$: C, 56.41; H, 3.20; N, 14.95%).

3-{4'-(4''-Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (8a-d) :

Compounds **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and formic acid (1 mL) in benzene (20–50 mL) were refluxed for 10–15 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off. To the reaction mixture ethanol (10 mL) was added and poured on crushed ice. The solid thus obtained was filtered and dried. It was treated with conc. sulphuric acid (10 mL) and poured

into ice cold water. The solid obtained was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous DMF. **8a** : Yield 76%, m.p. 167–168 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : 1615 (C=N), 1600 (C=C), 1249 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 755 (C–Cl); MS (m/z) : 442 (M^+), 344 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 55.90; H, 3.17; N, 16.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 56.05; H, 3.21; N, 16.35%); **8b** : Yield 60%, m.p. 118–120 °C (Found : C, 55.93; H, 3.18; N, 16.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 56.05; H, 3.21; N, 16.35%); **8c** : Yield 62%, m.p. 186–188 °C (Found : C, 55.98; H, 3.18; N, 16.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{OS}$: C, 56.05; H, 3.21; N, 16.35%); **8d** : Yield 57%, m.p. 188–190 °C (Found : C, 50.88; H, 2.60; N, 14.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{OS}$: C, 50.92; H, 2.65; N, 14.85%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-7H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazine-6(5H)-ones (9a-d) :

To a solution of **1a-d** (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 mL), chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) and a few drops of pyridine were added and refluxed for 5–7 h. Excess of benzene was distilled off and the residue was recrystallised from aqueous DMF. **9a** : Yield 67%, m.p. 156–157 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3200 (NH), 1682 (C=O), 1618 (C=N), 1520 (C–N), 1245 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 755 (C–Cl), MS (m/z) : 372 (M^+), 374 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 54.72; H, 3.45; N, 14.94. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 54.76; H, 3.48; N, 15.03%); **9b** : Yield 67%, m.p. 165–167 °C (Found : C, 54.73; H, 3.45; N, 14.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 54.76; H, 3.48; N, 15.03%); **9c** : Yield 56%, m.p. 200–202 °C (Found : C, 54.72; H, 3.42; N, 14.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 54.76; H, 3.48; N, 15.03%); **9d** : Yield 66%, m.p. 188–190 °C (Found : C, 50.05; H, 2.90; N, 13.67. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 50.12; H, 2.94; N, 13.75%).

6-Phenyl-5,6-dihydro-3-{4'-(chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (10a-d) :

A mixture of **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 mL) was refluxed for 15–20 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water, the product was filtered, dried and crystallized from CHCl_3 : MeOH (5 : 1). **10a** : Yield 69%, m.p. 188–190 °C; PMR : 2.87 (1H, s, CH), 5.20 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 7.12–7.90 (13H, m, Ar-H), 9.65 (1H, s, NH, D_2O exchange); MS (m/z) : 420 (M^+), 422 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 62.73; H, 3.95; N, 13.24. Calcd. for

$C_{22}H_{17}ClN_4O_2S$: C, 62.78; H, 4.04; N, 13.31%); **10b** : Yield 71%, m.p. 92–94 °C (Found : C, 62.70; H, 3.98; N, 13.21. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{17}ClN_4O_2S$: C, 62.78; H, 4.04; N, 13.31%); **10c** : Yield 56%, m.p. 230–232 °C (Found : C, 62.73; H, 3.99; N, 13.28. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{17}ClN_4O_2S$: C, 62.78; H, 4.04; N, 13.31%); **10d** : Yield 56%, m.p. 202–204 °C (Found : C, 57.90; H, 3.46; N, 12.23. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}Cl_2N_4O_2S$: C, 58.02; H, 3.51; N, 12.30%).

3-{4'-(Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]-iminoisatins (**11a-d**) :

A mixture of **1a-d** (0.01 mol) and isatin (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 mL) containing 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 2–4 h and left overnight at room

temperature. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from aqueous DMF. **11a** : Yield 70%, m.p. 213–214 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3380 (NH), 2558 (SH), 1683 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1525 (C-N), 1245 ($-CH_2O-$), 755 (C-Cl); MS (m/z) : 461 (M^+), 463 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 59.76; H, 3.41; N, 15.10. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{16}ClN_5O_2S$: C, 59.80; H, 3.46; N, 15.16%); **11b** : Yield 76%, m.p. 180–182 °C (Found : C, 59.70; H, 3.39; N, 15.10. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{16}ClN_5O_2S$: C, 59.80; H, 3.46; N, 15.16%); **11e** : Yield 60%, m.p. 248–250 °C (Found : C, 59.78; H, 3.41; N, 15.13. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{16}ClN_5O_2S$: C, 59.80; H, 3.46; N, 15.16%); **11d** : Yield 78%, m.p. >250 °C (Found : C, 55.50; H, 2.89; N, 14.04. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{15}Cl_2N_5O_2S$: C, 55.64; H, 3.02; N, 14.11%).

1a-11a : $R_1 = Cl, R_2 = H, R_3 = H$

1b-11b : $R_1 = H, R_2 = Cl, R_3 = H$

1c-11c : $R_1 = H, R_2 = H, R_3 = Cl$

1d-11d : $R_1 = Cl, R_2 = H, R_3 = Cl$

- (a) $N_2H_4 \cdot H_2O$, DMF; (b) CS_2 , KOH, EtOH; (c) PhCOOH, $POCl_3$; (d) PhCH(OH)COPh, KOH, *n*-propanol; (e) PhCOCH₂Br, MeCOO⁻Na⁺ DMF; (f) PhNCS, DMF; (g) HCOOH, C_6H_6 ; (h) ClCOCH₂Cl, C_5H_5N , C_6H_6 ; (i) PhCHO, DMF; (j) isatin, EtOH, AcOH

Scheme 1

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